

SOCIOECONOMIC FACTORS THAT AFFECT LOW-INCOME COLLEGE STUDENTS'
MENTAL HEALTH

by

Zhi Tan

ORCID ID: 0009-0008-2840-4011

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11552394

A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements to Graduate with University Honors

The University Honors Program
California State University, Fullerton
May 2024

Approved by:

Adrian Rodriguez

Dr. Adrian Rodriguez, Department of Human Services

Stacy Mallicoat

Dr. Stacy Mallicoat, Director, University Honors Program

Date:

5/17/2024

5/24/2024

Abstract

The world has changed drastically due to the three-year COVID-19 pandemic including significant impacts on mental health in society. This thesis will analyze the socioeconomic factors that affected low-income college students' mental health during this pandemic. A qualitative analysis using Long-Sutehall et al's, (2010) method of secondary data involving interviews and case studies will be utilized to determine these factors. The research will emphasize the heightened financial burdens experienced by students with reduced income including greater stress and struggle. With increased economic hardship, students were more likely to experience symptoms of depression and anxiety due to their numerous responsibilities. A lack of accessible technologies was a significant hinderance on their academic success. Students also described increased familial responsibility, where they were often required to assume a caregiving role for family members in addition to pursuing their education. Prior interviews from twelve participants across ten published studies were analyzed. The following four themes were identified: 1.) decrease in income, 2.) mental health symptoms (e.g., anxiety and depression), 3.) technology limitations, and 4.) increased responsibilities for their family. By understanding the relationships between socioeconomic factors and mental well-being, researchers can work towards creating a more equitable and supportive environment for all students. Faculty, administrators, and mental health counselors can utilize the findings of this research to provide different support services that address these specific needs. Recognizing and addressing these factors may include initiatives to reduce financial barriers, expand access to mental health services and social support networks, and creating supportive learning environments with access to required technologies.

Literature Review

The emergence of SARS-CoV-2 in December 2019 ignited the COVID-19 pandemic, rapidly spreading across the globe despite initial efforts by Chinese authorities to contain it in Wuhan (Lee, 2021). With symptoms like the flu, COVID-19 spreads through airborne transmission or aerosol, leading to rapid spreading of the virus. The lack of comprehensive understanding of the virus's attributes and history resulted in a surge of cases worldwide, prompting the World Health Organization (WHO) to declare it a global pandemic on March 11, 2020 (WHO TEAM, 2021). In response to the alarming rates of infection and mortality, governments implemented strict measures such as shutdowns to attempt to control the spread of the virus (COVID-19 Timeline, n.d.). This literature review aims to explore the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the mental health of low-income students, who faced socio-economic challenges during this global crisis.

Due to the surge in COVID-19 cases, subsequent global shutdown and widespread uncertainty led to significant impacts on both income and education which has exacerbated college students' anxiety levels. Bryant and Welding (2023) reported that in 2022, 35% of students were diagnosed with stress, while 27% exhibited symptoms of depression. Mental health disorders are associated with heightened feelings of fear and uncertainty, which can escalate the risk of various medical conditions such as heart disease, diabetes, and depression (NIH, 2016). Among the array of anxiety disorders, generalized anxiety and panic disorders are prevalent. Generalized anxiety disorder involves persistent worrying about everyday concerns like health, finances, or family matters, often accompanied by difficulties in relaxation and concentration, leading to insomnia. Despite the substantial prevalence of anxiety disorders affecting around 40 million individuals, treatment remains underutilized, with only 36.9%

receiving appropriate care. A poll conducted in the spring of 2020 underscored the widespread negative impact on adults' mental health, with at least 45% reporting adverse effects due to various pandemic-related stressors (COVID-19 and Behavioral Health, n.d.).

Socioeconomic Factors

Socioeconomic factors encompass a variety of external factors that significantly contribute to our well-being (Social & Economic Factors, n.d.). More specifically, the stability of these factors can positively impact our health and mental health. These external factors include income, education, community, and healthcare. Furthermore, these external factors also influence us internally, encompassing our mental state, personality traits, attitudes, and lifestyle choices (Chen et al., 2023). Socioeconomic stability creates opportunities for other factors including food, and insurance, to enhance living standards and our overall welfare (Social & Economic Factors, n.d.).

Income and education are essential determinants influencing housing choices and various aspects of lifestyle (Income, n.d.). Individuals with above average incomes have access to a broader range of options, including healthier food choices, employment opportunities, and higher-quality housing and educational facilities. During the COVID-19 pandemic, income became a crucial factor determining both physical and mental well-being. Individuals with higher incomes were better equipped to withstand the psychological and financial impacts of the pandemic, while those with lower incomes experienced greater adversity (Piacentini, 2022). The disruption caused by COVID-19 also reshaped perceptions of education globally, prompting an abrupt shift from traditional in-person learning to online modalities.

Education plays a crucial role in shaping individuals' perspectives, fostering social growth, and influencing life-altering decisions (Konig, 2013). Access to higher education is often

considered a privilege, as financial constraints and lack of support can hinder students' ability to attend college (A History of Privilege in American Higher Education, 2021). Research indicates that higher education correlates with increased income, expanded employment opportunities, and healthier lifestyle choices. It is estimated that each additional year of schooling results in an 11% rise in annual income, alongside a safer work environment and access to benefits such as health insurance and sick leave. Moreover, education is associated with reduced stress levels, lower rates of drug use, and decreased risks of various diseases including diabetes and depression (Education, n.d.). The COVID-19 pandemic brought about significant disruptions, leading to shifts where education was no longer considered a priority. These global changes in educational practices had profound impacts on students' mental health, contributing to heightened anxiety and self-doubt. Research indicates that approximately 95% of college students have experienced adverse health symptoms due to the pandemic, with nearly half acknowledging that mental health concerns have affected their academic performance (95% of College Students' Mental Health Impacted by COVID-19).

Society During COVID-19

As COVID-19 cases increased, many states and local governments responded by implementing restrictions to attempt to control the spread of the virus and reducing the number of casualties such as imposing lockdowns and stay-at-home orders (COVID-19 State and Local Government Issues, n.d.). While some businesses remained operational during the lockdown, safety measures resulted in workforce reductions, leading to job losses or decreased work hours for many employees. A study revealed that over 50% of parents supporting college-bound students experienced job loss, reduced work hours, or complete loss of income. Consequently, two-thirds of college students had to reassess their financial situations.

Research published found that first-generation college students experienced heightened financial anxiety when comparing their financial status to their peers (Welding, 2022). Low-income, first-generation students encountered greater challenges and achieved lower levels of success compared to their other schoolmates. Low-income college students are identified as students who have an annual income of less than \$25,000 (Engle & Tinto, n.d.) According to the National Center for Education Statistics, low-income, first-generation students were more likely to drop out of higher education, with 43% failing to earn their degree.

Crampton and McMinn (2021) noted that state leaders faced daunting decisions in combating the virus, particularly with limited information available (para 1). Implementing stay-at-home policies aimed at protecting residents often resulted in business closures and increased unemployment rates. However, failure to enforce such measures risked higher death tolls and accelerated virus transmission. According to Crampton and McMinn (2021), states that imposed stricter restrictions, including stay-at-home orders and mask mandates, experienced lower death rates and hospitalizations, albeit at the expense of poorer economic and educational outcomes (para 6).

The impact of COVID-19 restrictions disproportionately affected young adults aged 18-29, who are more likely to hold part-time or temporary jobs. Employment levels in this demographic dropped significantly more than in older age groups, which exacerbated financial strain and impeded career development opportunities. This economic disruption and limited experiences due to the global shutdown have contributed to heightened emotional distress among young adults, as evidenced by reports of increased levels of depression, anxiety, and alcohol dependence among students facing financial difficulties (Welding, 2022). Such emotional distress served as a risk factor for mental health disorders, including anxiety and depression

(Coulaud, 2023). The uncertainty surrounding job security and the duration of the pandemic worsened individuals' anxiety about their financial stability and prospects. As the United States grappled with soaring debt levels, both at the national and individual levels, financial instability became increasingly pervasive. The resultant inflation further strained individuals' ability to afford necessities, impacting their social relationships and educational pursuits.

Education During COVID-19

There were also challenges as “the shift from class-based to online learning has not been smooth for most universities and colleges.” The article states how students had difficulties adjusting; connectivity, and internet issues (Mseleku, 2020). The immediate shutdown resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic brought about significant disruptions in the education system, compelling educators to adapt to virtual teaching methods and instruct students remotely, while quarantining at home. However, this transition has revealed drawbacks among educators who lacked technological proficiency, hindering the effectiveness of remote instruction. Additionally, Muluye and Tadesse (2020) highlighted the challenges faced by parents, many of whom lacked access to essential Information and Communication Technology (ICT) infrastructure such as computers, radio, and television, necessary for facilitating distance learning (para 1). Disparities in technology resources and supportive learning environments worsen inequalities, as some students have better access to resources and suitable study spaces than others due to their socioeconomic status. (Sahu, 2020). Monitoring tests and assignments poses additional challenges in the virtual setting, potentially disadvantaging students who lack access to necessary technology resources.

The abrupt transition to online learning due to the COVID-19 pandemic has raised concerns among students and faculty regarding the sufficiency of resources to facilitate this

change specifically in technology. Universities were ill-equipped for the abrupt transition to virtual instruction, resulting in increased demand for technology and connectivity among students who were not prepared or lacked the financial means to acquire necessary equipment for the change. This then raises the concern for students who do not have access to laptops and internet connectivity. (Sahu, 2020). "Students who do not have an Internet facility will suffer a clear disadvantage while participating in the evaluation process" (Sahu, 2020, para 6). This disparity in access to technology and conducive study environments has raised concerns about equity in education. Professors also play a pivotal role in students' academic success, yet many may lack the necessary support to assist students effectively in this new online learning landscape. However, the pandemic has prompted significant technological adaptations to enhance support for remote learning such as video conferencing tools such as Zoom, and learning systems such as Canvas to access educational materials, and communicate, potentially better preparing society to address similar challenges in the future.

Conclusion

The study of the COVID-19 pandemic's impact on socioeconomic factors holds significant importance in contemporary society, given its enduring repercussions and the potential lessons it offers for future global events. Throughout the pandemic, profound changes unfolded, particularly affecting the income and education of college students, with consequences both beneficial and burdensome for society. These changes were compounded by the responsibilities students juggled, involving their families, educators, colleagues, and more. There are government entities, educational institutions, and businesses provided crucial resources to support students in navigating mental health challenges during these unprecedented times, however, it is not enough to sustain. The adaptability demonstrated in response to the pandemic

underscores the importance of integrating similar practices into future educational endeavors, facilitating enhanced learning experiences for students.

Methodology

The CSUF Pollak Library's OneSearch database was utilized to identify relevant qualitative articles and case studies for analysis. The keywords used to locate these articles include: Qualitative COVID-19 College Students, College Students' Mental Health, and low-income college students. The selected articles ranged in publication date from 2020 to 2023 and included a majority from peer-reviewed journals with a few from other educational sites. The topics covered include mental health, education conditions of low-income college students, and socioeconomic factors including income disparities that led to technological disruptions in learning, and increased of family responsibilities which affected their mental health.

Study Inclusion

The methodology consisted of a qualitative model using a case study research method to address the research question. An article by Mishra and Dey, (2022) provided a roadmap for identifying themes in case study-focused qualitative research. The authors emphasized the importance of understanding themes and outlines through a systematic process for theme development. Using qualitative methods, systematic reviews of interviews from peer reviewed articles were used to provide the background context and to investigate socioeconomic factors that affected low-income college students' mental health.

Long-Sutthall's (2010) approach to conducting secondary analysis from primary qualitative datasets was also utilized. Based on the secondary research conducted, the qualitative research provided an in-depth analysis using case study models for the research focus. There were ten case studies or systematic reviews that were used and were limited to English peer-reviewed

articles. The following developmental questions guided the present study's analysis of the pre-existing: 1.) Are low-income college students more likely to have depression symptoms?, 2.) Are low-income college students more likely to have technical disruptions which lead to higher stress and anxiety?, 3.) Will a decrease in income for low-income college students due to the pandemic lead to greater stress?, 4.) How does taking care of family members during the pandemic lead to disruptions in low-income students' education?

Participants

Various participants were used to represent the research that included both females and males, primarily low-income college students. A total of twelve participants provided their statements of how COVID-19 had affected them differently.

Results

Based on the analysis of ten case studies, qualitative interview data from twelve participants were analyzed to identify the major themes regarding socioeconomic factors that affected low-income college students' (LCS) mental health. These included increased symptoms of anxiety and depression due to the difficulty transitioning to online learning. Relatedly, difficulty accessing required technology to navigate the new online environment also affected their anxiety and increased their stress. The effects of decrease in income or job loss due to the pandemic similarly led to greater stress, while caring for family members reduced the amount of time available to focus on their studies.

Anxiety and Depression

The pandemic served as the escalation of anxiety disorders and depression symptoms. Among the five participants examined, their feedback echoed a similar sentiment, all expressing a detrimental impact on their mental well-being.

In an article, it mentions “anxiety disorders were one of the most common diagnoses given to these individuals. United States adults were more than 3 times as likely to be diagnosed with depression or anxiety disorders in April/May of 2020 compared to pre-pandemic rates” (Dahl et.al., 2022). While various mental health issues were revealed in the article, the major emphasis was on anxiety and depression-related concerns. Participants also endorsed increased symptoms of anxiety as was reported by other groups. There were multiple similar responses from different participants as they mentioned similarly “I have felt very anxious and alone during this time”; “COVID-19 pandemic has impact[ed] my personal mental health, I feel more anxious and worried most of the time because COVID-19 is out there and no one is basically safe”; and “I feel increased anxiety when going (Dahl et.al., 2022).

One individual (participant 1) spoke about the effects on their mental health due to the pandemic. They stated:

COVID-19 has negatively affected my mental health. I struggle with depression and anxiety and the emergence of the pandemic has made my symptoms worse... But I would say that I’ve experienced more bouts of depression, worry, anxiety, hopelessness, panic, and numbness than I’ve ever had in 1 year before. (Dahl et.al., 2022).

Participant 2 similarly detailed how their emotions and the pandemic contributed to their mental health:

I was experiencing high levels of anxiety, fear, and numbness. I would ping pong between feeling like it’s going to be okay, and then feeling dread and overwhelm, and then feeling numb, and back again—usually all in 1 day! (Dahl et.al., 2022).

Participant 3 also stated about how depression also affected them as well. They stated, “As of recently I feel that the pandemic has had a negative impact on my mental wellbeing. I

have stopped reaching out to my support and care less about completing school.” (Dahl et.al., 2022).

Participant 15 explains her situation as she battles from chronic depression during COVID-19. “I actually suffer from chronic depression. [COVID-19] has definitely made it a lot worse, just being in isolation and being home 24/7. It feels like I need to get out but there’s nowhere to go” (Son 2020).

Another article discusses how the COVID-19 lockdown has created mental stress and sudden changes that negatively impact students' mental health. College students are especially susceptible to developing psychological disorders, as demonstrated by various studies. Additionally, students with pre-existing health conditions have reported heightened levels of anxiety and depression. (Gupta & Agrawal, 2021).

All participants analyzed in the sources reported experiencing heightened symptoms of either anxiety or depression. This commonality underscores the significant impact of mental health challenges among the study group. The findings in the following show a reduction in personal income which reveals its significant impact on the mental health of individuals.

Job Loss and Income

The pandemic heightened anxiety disorders and depression symptoms, with financial strains significantly impacting the mental well-being of the five participants analyzed. Their feedback uniformly highlighted the negative effects of financial challenges on their mental health.

Participant 4 mentioned COVID-19 has placed a significant financial burden on me and my family and has therefore had an impact on my daily anxiety”; Currently, due to lack of work, my finances have been challenged, which has affected my mental wellbeing

intensely; and I lost my job and all my classes moved online and the lack of socialization made me more depressed (Dahl et.al., 2022).

A participant (participant 5) is also experiencing financial struggles as she needs to relocate. She mentions the struggles of losing her job and stated,

Not only was I laid off from my job, but I had to move overseas to my military family's station with only one backpack. Now I'm paying for the school to store my belongings and pay full tuition without a job or bedroom. I'm sleeping on a floor, babysitting my siblings full time on top of 15.5 units (Hoyt et.al., 2021).

Participant 6 similarly described her family income as inadequate during this time:

I currently have no income coming in and it has been really rough for my family, as I live in a single-parent household where annual income is [$< \$15,000$]. My mom also currently has no job at the moment too due the closure of her work due to the virus. It's rough trying to pay for rent at home and my upcoming apartment rent with no work. We're having to result to our [sic] savings which should've been for my and my younger sister's college tuition (Hoyt et.al., 2021).

There was a report of loss of personal income, such as participant 7 who said, “I'm extra broke and depressed, the job I thought I was going to start is no longer available to me” (Hoyt et.al., 2021).

Financial struggles among college students are prompting thoughts of discontinuing their studies. The mere consideration of leaving school or transferring to another institution due to severe financial strain instills a sense of fear. Additionally, students who are away from home are facing challenges in meeting basic needs such as rent and food expenses, as their financial resources dwindle (Gupta & Agrawal, 2021).

Participant 12 explains his situation as a student worker where he is doing food deliveries “during coronavirus to try and get money for their family. Other students do not have to work during this time; as a lower-income student, my family depends on me bringing in some type of money year-round” (Kiebler & Stewart 2021).

In another survey conducted by Rodriguez-Planas (2022), a survey was administered via email, and out of the 15,982 college students, 3,163 students responded to the survey. Results shown that “two thirds of students who lost their jobs due to the pandemic reported either being laid-off or furloughed. Overall, 35% of QC students saw their wage and salary earnings decrease because of the pandemic” (Rodriguez-Planas, 2022). Students still then continued to have difficulties to find a replacement job. Due to their decrease in income, students were to seek financial assistance such as emergency grants and CARES Act.

According to Rudenstine (2020), during periods of significant life disruption like unemployment, financial savings can offer a reassuring sense of stability and security. The COVID-19 pandemic notably intensified this need, as evidenced by the substantial rise in unemployment rates in the United States, soaring from 3.6% to 14.7% between January 2020 and April 2020. Particularly vulnerable were individuals already grappling with socioeconomic disadvantages, who bore the brunt of the sudden income loss.

Students voiced concern about the financial pressure stemming from family members experiencing decreased work hours, job layoffs, or multiple job losses, all leading to reduced household income and increasing expenses amid an unpredictable economic future constrained by the pandemic (Farris, 2021).

The pandemic has exacerbated anxiety disorders and depression symptoms, particularly due to financial strains, as observed among the participants examined. Their consistent feedback

underscores the profound impact of financial challenges on mental well-being. The following topic explores the effects of technological disruptions on students' concentration, resulting in heightened stress levels.

Technology

Similar responses were observed among groups of participants who experienced disruptions caused by technology, leading to difficulties in concentration. These disruptions hindered their ability to focus and complete tasks effectively, resulting in heightened frustration and decreased productivity. The shared experiences explain the significant impact of technological interruptions on cognitive functioning and overall well-being in the following,

COVID-19 pandemic has affected college students' well-being, with many students describing specific stressors within their shelter-in-place environments, such as a lack of access to technology (e.g., “I do not have stable Internet at home”) and quiet places to work/study (e.g., “[my siblings] do not give me enough quiet time for my classes”). (Hoyt et.al., 2021).

Students faced difficulties accessing online tools, even though they possessed digital learning devices and internet data, due to poor network connectivity at home. The critical issue of unreliable internet connections for online learning, compounded by poor home network infrastructure, emerged as a significant barrier to the participation of many students in online educational activities (Mseleku, 2020). While online learning offers numerous benefits such as the ability for instructors to teach remotely, unrestricted opportunities, and the potential to promote effective online teaching practices, challenges arise when faced with low internet speeds or poor connections. It is “perceive it as a forceful implied obligation for them.” Students in technical departments express resistance because online platforms often cannot effectively

demonstrate complex concepts practically (Gupta & Agrawal, 2021). Online courses struggle to meet students' interaction needs and lack the personalized touch, continuous support, and feedback that are vital for effective learning. Overall, the passage suggests that while online learning offers convenience, it may not adequately address the diverse learning needs of students, particularly in technical fields” (Gupta & Agrawal, 2021).

Participants affected by technological disruptions reported similar challenges, notably difficulties in concentration. These interruptions impeded their ability to focus and complete tasks efficiently, leading to heightened frustration and decreased productivity. These findings underscore the profound impact of technology-related disruptions on cognitive functioning and overall well-being. The following topic explores how students have faced interruptions in their education due to increased caregiving responsibilities for family members.

Family Responsibilities

Groups of participants experiencing interruptions to their academic pursuits due to increased caregiving responsibilities for family members during the pandemic exhibited similar responses. These individuals faced challenges in balancing their academic obligations with caregiving duties, resulting in disruptions to their educational progress. The shared experiences highlight the significant impact of caregiving responsibilities on academic pursuits during this challenging time.

Participant 8, mentions the necessity of spending money to support his mother and sister during the COVID-19 crisis, identifying himself as the "man of the house" responsible for covering bills and providing for his family while simultaneously pursuing his education.

My mother...she's a housekeeper and plus with COVID... She works at Hilton and she's out of a job right now so I've been trying to help a lot [...] I had to buy her a laptop for her to do

all that [responsibilities, bills] online. It's another expense I had, but it was to help her with that you know, trying to get the cheapest laptop. Even though my sister is older, I started to help her a lot, like I sent her some money yesterday so she could get an uber home or for food sometimes (Eden et. Al., 2021).

Another participant 9, a single parent, and a student needs to support her family without any childcare services. She explains the financial responsibilities as a single parent needing to care for her two children, and how the pandemic has pressured her. She states

We rely completely on me, I have an adult son who's autistic and not able to find employment. And I'm trying to help him through life and then, I have a young daughter who's in elementary school and so all the financial [responsibilities] — How we put food on the table, how we keep the car running, how we keep our cell phones on all of that falls on my shoulders (Eden et. Al., 2021).

Gamora, participant 10 reveals that she lacked the financial resources to sustain residence in the dormitories. Upon returning home due to financial constraints, she forfeited her designated study area. Furthermore, as the eldest child, she assumed familial duties, which impeded her academic progress. The absence of an ideal learning setting and increased familial obligations consequently hindered her academic performance. She states

I was dorming the university and then I had to go back home and then make, and then I had to find housing for the next year and make sure it was affordable do I want to go back to Berkeley and I personally I'm back in my hometown or with my family, I can't have that academic space, you know I had so much more responsibilities (Eden et. Al., 2021).

Participant 11 mentioned “I end up doing all the house responsibilities, including cooking. I’ve been falling behind on my schoolwork because I’m taking care of my family and they’re also really loud and hectic. I miss my quiet on campus apartment” (Farris, 2021).

Participants who assumed increased caregiving responsibilities for family members during the pandemic faced interruptions to their academic pursuits, yielding similar responses. Struggling to balance caregiving duties with academic obligations, these individuals encountered disruptions to their educational progress. This underscores the profound impact of caregiving responsibilities on academic pursuits amid these trying circumstances.

Conclusion

The research findings consistently identified socioeconomic factors impacting the mental health of low-income college students (LCS). These factors included heightened levels of anxiety and depression attributed to challenges in transitioning to online learning. Moreover, limited access to necessary technology increased anxiety and stress levels. Concurrently, pandemic-induced job loss intensified stress levels among this demographic. Additionally, the responsibility of caring for family members during the pandemic further constrained their ability to dedicate time to academic pursuits.

Discussion

This systematic review sought to uncover key themes of socioeconomic factors that impacted low-income college students' mental health. The case study analysis revealed the following four themes related to the impact of the COVID-19 shutdown on LCS: 1. increased depression and anxiety, 2. technological disruptions, 3. impacts of job loss and loss of income, 4. family responsibilities and caregiving. The review highlights the increased likelihood of depression and anxiety among low-income college students during the pandemic. The significant mental health burden faced by these individuals was aggravated by the economic and social disruptions brought about by COVID-19. The impact of limited access to technology and disruptions in connectivity also affected mental health and academic performance as it hindered their ability to engage effectively in remote learning. The decrease in income and increased financial burdens experienced by these individuals heightened their anxiety and exacerbated existing mental health challenges. There were also additional responsibilities placed on low-income college students to care for family members during the pandemic, which led to interruptions in their academic pursuits. This analysis discusses how the COVID-19 lockdown has created mental stress and sudden changes that negatively impact students' mental health. College students are especially susceptible to developing psychological disorders, as demonstrated by various studies. Additionally, students with pre-existing health conditions have reported heightened levels of anxiety and depression.

The scarcity of information on these topics of technical disruptions and family responsibilities emphasizes a gap in our understanding, highlighting areas where societal awareness may be lacking. The current study's findings suggest these issues should be investigated in further detail as it is evident that these issues need more comprehensive

exploration and explanation. Understanding these topics is essential for shedding light on their complexities and the potential impact on others. By expanding upon the discussion, researchers can offer valuable insights, identify key factors, and uncover potential solutions. This will provide a foundation for informed decision-making and better recommendations for mental health support.

By identifying key themes and similarities, this review provides a comprehensive understanding of challenges faced by this demographic. These factors provide insight into challenges faced by low-income college students during COVID-19. By understanding their difficulties, academic institutions can create a more supportive environment. There should be more awareness about mental health challenges and how to provide support for students. A primary recommendation would be providing accessible mental health services to support students, educating and spreading awareness, and self-care practices.

Recommendations

To enhance mental health services on college campuses, several recommendations can be made based on the existing services. Campuses should ensure the availability of mental health professionals, including psychologists, counselors, social workers, and psychiatrists, to cater to the varied needs of students. Moreover, campuses should consider expanding their pool of mental health professionals by hiring graduate- and postgraduate-level trainees, thereby increasing the capacity to provide counseling and support services. Also, campuses should prioritize improving staffing ratios by hiring more mental health professionals to ensure adequate support for students, particularly given the increased demand for services (Qing & Constantouros, et al. 2021).

Student fees largely support campus mental health services, it's essential for campuses to prioritize transparent and equitable fee breakdown structures. This includes ensuring that fee levels are reasonable and affordable for all students, with provisions for financial assistance or waivers for low-income students. Additionally, campuses should explore alternative funding sources, such as state appropriations and external grants, to supplement student fees and expand mental health services. By diversifying funding streams, campuses can lessen financial barriers and ensure the sustainability of mental health programs in the long term. To address these challenges, campuses can provide accessible mental health services to support students. These include counseling sessions led by licensed professionals like psychologists, clinical social workers, and clinical counselors. Crisis interventions, such as hotlines, are available for students in immediate need. Additionally, universities offer outreach programs like trainings, workshops, peer support groups, and online resources (Qing & Constantouros, et al. 2021). Individuals can implement a combination of self-care practices and mental health support. Self-care practices, such as exercising, engaging in hobbies, and spending time outdoors can reduce stress and promote relaxation. Simultaneously, seeking professional help from counselors and maintaining connections with loved ones and pets provide crucial mental health support (NIMH, n.d.). By integrating both self-care and professional assistance, individuals can effectively manage the challenges posed by the pandemic and safeguard their mental health.

By addressing these concerns faced by LCS, society can create a more supportive environment that allows students to thrive. This research emphasizes the importance of proactive measures from faculty, administrators, and mental health counselors in building resilience and providing support services, such as efforts to ease financial hardships, expand access to mental health resources, and establish support networks within higher education institutions. Ultimately,

these recommendations aim to strengthen the accessibility, affordability, and effectiveness of mental health services on college campuses, promoting academic success and overall student thriving.

Strengths and Limitations

Strengths of this systematic review include its focus on researching the socioeconomic factors impacting low-income college students' mental health. All articles utilized in the review underwent peer-review or were sourced from reputable educational outlets, ensuring a high standard of credibility.

However, there are limitations to consider. This study relies on secondary analysis rather than primary interviews, which may limit the depth of insight into the experiences of low-income college students. Additionally, the research was conducted by an individual rather than a team, potentially introducing bias into the analysis. Furthermore, the review's scope is constrained by the articles' time period, mainly focusing on data from 2020-2021. This limited timeframe may overlook potential changes and developments in mental health outcomes, particularly considering the dynamic nature of the COVID-19 pandemic and the subsequent interventions and relief efforts implemented.

Future Directions

To better understand how to help low-income college students with their mental health, researchers can talk directly to these students to hear about their experiences and challenges and develop research through primary sources as this can show what they're going through.

Researchers can follow these students over time to see how their mental health changes and what factors might be influencing it. It is significant for researchers to consider all the different parts of a student's identity and demographics because these factors can all affect mental health in

different ways. Researchers can check if the programs and support services available to these students are working and determine if financial aid or counseling services are making a difference in how students feel. By working together, they can come up with better ways to support low-income college students' mental health that consider all aspects of their lives.

Conclusion

This systematic review is about socioeconomic factors affecting the mental health of low-income college students, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. By identifying key themes and similarities, the review provides a comprehensive understanding of the challenges faced by this demographic, including heightened depression and anxiety, economic strains, limited access to technology, and increased caregiving responsibilities. To address these challenges, recommendations have been proposed to enhance mental health services on college campuses. Despite the strengths of this review, there are limitations to consider, including reliance on secondary analysis and potential bias. Future research directions include conducting primary interviews, exploring longitudinal approaches, and assessing the effectiveness of support programs. This review is not the first to examine mental health issues about college students. To further advance understanding in this area, future research could explore the long-term effects of socioeconomic factors on the mental health of low-income college students beyond the immediate context of the COVID-19 pandemic.

References

- Bryant, J., & Welding, L. (2023, May 15). College student mental health statistics: BestColleges. BestColleges.com. <https://www.bestcolleges.com/research/college-student-mental-health-statistics/#:~:text=Data%20Summary,anxiety%3B%2027%25%20had%20depression>
- Carlisle, K. (2024, May 20). JHS 41st edition spring 2022 final.docx. Google. <https://docs.google.com/document/d/e/2PACX-1vTcwWKCuYRlIszbnjeV2FuUujcw20IcCr1BX5YYtnpQXXqiXpvYd5Sa5JN4OUiHKQ/pub>
- National Institute of Mental Health. (2024, May 13). Caring for your mental health. U.S. Department of Health and Human Services. <https://www.nimh.nih.gov/health/topics/caring-for-your-mental-health>
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2022, August 16). CDC museum COVID-19 timeline. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. <https://www.cdc.gov/museum/timeline/covid19.html#:~:text=March%2011%2C%202020declares%20COVID%2D19%20a%20pandemic>
- Coulaud, P.-J., et al. (2023, March). Moderation of the association between COVID-19-related income loss and depression by receipt of financial support: Repeated cross-sectional surveys of young adults in Canada and France (2020-2021). SSM - Population Health. U.S. National Library of Medicine. [https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9832713/#:~:text=Overall%2C%20half%20reported%20depressive%20symptoms,%25%20\(in%20both%20surveys\)](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9832713/#:~:text=Overall%2C%20half%20reported%20depressive%20symptoms,%25%20(in%20both%20surveys))

Crampton, L., & McMinn, S. (2021). COVID's deadly tradeoffs, by the numbers: How each state has fared in the pandemic. Politico. <https://politico.com/interactives/2021/covid-by-the-numbers-how-each-state-fared-on-our-pandemic-scorecard/>

Chen, D.-P., et al. (2023). Exploration of the external and internal factors that affected learning effectiveness for the students: A questionnaire survey. BMC Medical Education. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-023-04035-4>

Primary Care Development Corporation. (2020, August 21). COVID-19 and behavioral health. https://www.pcdc.org/covid-19-and-behavioral-health/?creative=587372847111&keyword=covid+and+mental+health&matchtype=p&network=g&device=c&gad=1&gclid=CjwKCAjwov6hBhBsEiwAvrvN6PjdCGHIbjm6Z_iGftOfrzeGcgO3-5Mv-hykK0yMNpDYoNly9F4S0xoCSBgQAvD_BwE

Manatt. (n.d.). COVID-19 state and local government issues. <https://manatt.com/navigating-covid-19/state-and-local-government-issues>

Eden, N., et al. (2024, May 20). COVID-19's impacts on learning environments and educational performance of low-income first-generation college students. <https://irle.berkeley.edu/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/COVID-19s-Impacts-on-Learning-Environments-and-Educational-Performance-of-Low-Income-First-Generation-College-Students-1.pdf>

Engle, J., & Tinto, V. (2024, May 13). Moving beyond access. ERIC - Department of Education. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED504448.pdf>

Farris, S. G., et al. (2024, May 20). [Http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0887302x07303626](http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0887302x07303626) | Request PDF. ResearchGate.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328039672_httpjournalsagepubcomdoiabs1011770887302X07303626

Gupta, R., & Agrawal, R. (2021, December). Are the concerns destroying mental health of college students?: A qualitative analysis portraying experiences amidst COVID-19 ambiguities. *Analyses of Social Issues and Public Policy: ASAP*. U.S. National Library of Medicine. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8013217/>

Konig, T. (2023, July 24). 5 key ways education influences future success. Riverside College. <https://riversidecollege.co.za/ways-education-influences-future-success/>

Lee, J., et al. (2021, June 8). Impact of COVID-19 on the mental health of US college students. *BMC Psychology*. BioMed Central. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-021-00598-3>

Long-Sutehall, T., et al. (2024, May 13). Secondary analysis of qualitative data: A valuable method for ... University of Wolverhampton. <https://www.wlv.ac.uk/media/wlv/pdf/Secondary-analysis-JRN3815531.pdf>

Mishra, S., & Dey, A. K. (2022, October 27). Understanding and identifying “themes” in qualitative case ... Sage Journals. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/22779779221134659>

Mseleku, Z. (2024, May 13). A literature review of e-learning and e-teaching in the ... *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*. <https://ijisrt.com/assets/upload/files/IJISRT20OCT430.pdf>

Piacentini, J., et al. (2024, May 20). The impact of COVID-19 on labor markets and inequality. U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics. <https://www.bls.gov/osmr/research-papers/2022/ec220060.htm>

Qing, L., et al. (2021, December 10). Overview of mental health services for college students.

Legislative Analyst's Office. <https://lao.ca.gov/Publications/Report/4481>

Rodríguez-Planas, N. (2022, January 28). Hitting where it hurts most: COVID-19 and low-

income urban college students. *Economics of Education Review*, Pergamon.

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0272775722000103>

Rudenshine, S., et al. (2021, February). Depression and anxiety during the COVID-19 pandemic

in an urban, low-income public university sample. *Journal of Traumatic Stress*. U.S.

National Library of Medicine. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7675401/>

Sahu, P. (2020, April 4). Closure of universities due to coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19):

Impact on education and mental health of students and academic staff. *Cureus*.

<https://www.cureus.com/articles/30110#!/>

Son1, C., et al. (2024, May 20). Effects of COVID-19 on college students' mental health in the

United States: Interview survey study. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*. JMIR

Publications Inc., Toronto, Canada. <https://www.jmir.org/2020/9/e21279/>

Staff Writers. (2021, December 16). A history of privilege in higher education: BestColleges.

BestColleges.com. [https://www.bestcolleges.com/news/analysis/2020/07/17/history-privilege-higher-](https://www.bestcolleges.com/news/analysis/2020/07/17/history-privilege-higher-education/#:~:text=Higher%20education%20began%20as%20a,learning%20in%20the%2021st%20century)

[education/#:~:text=Higher%20education%20began%20as%20a,learning%20in%20the%2021st%20century](https://www.bestcolleges.com/news/analysis/2020/07/17/history-privilege-higher-education/#:~:text=Higher%20education%20began%20as%20a,learning%20in%20the%2021st%20century)

Staff Writers. (2022, October 18). 95% of college students' mental health impacted by COVID-

19: BestColleges. BestColleges.com. [https://www.bestcolleges.com/research/college-](https://www.bestcolleges.com/research/college-mental-health-impacts-from-covid19)

[mental-health-impacts-from-covid19](https://www.bestcolleges.com/research/college-mental-health-impacts-from-covid19)

National Institutes of Health. (2017, September 8). Understanding anxiety disorders. U.S. Department of Health and Human Services.

<https://newsinhealth.nih.gov/2016/03/understanding-anxiety-disorders>

Welding, L. (2022, May 16). 6 ways college finances affect mental health: BestColleges.

BestColleges.com. <https://www.bestcolleges.com/blog/college-finances-affect-mental-health/>